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A Study in the Complex Formation of Thiodiacetic, Thiodipropionic, Dithiodiacetic, Iminodiacetic and Oxydiacetic Acids with Nickel and Copper Ions

S. N. DUBEY,* R. K. BAWEJA and D. M. PURI

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University,
Kurukshetra-132 119

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A survey of the literature¹⁻⁴ revealed that no effort appears to have been made to determine the thermodynamic stability constants of the complexes formed by Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} ions with thiodiacetic acid (TDAA), thiodipropionic acid (TDPA), dithiodiacetic acid (DTDAA), iminodiacetic acid (IDAA) and oxydiacetic acid (ODAA). In view of the above and also the results reported⁵⁻⁷ by us on the chelation abilities of the above mentioned ligands, it was considered of interest to study Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} systems potentiometrically. The thermodynamic stability constants of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes were obtained by extrapolating the determined stability constants at various ionic strengths (0.1, 0.2 and 0.3 M, 25°) to zero ionic strength. The thermodynamic functions (ΔG , ΔH and ΔS) were calculated at 0.1 M. The titration technique adopted was that of Calvin and Wilson as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁸⁻¹⁰.

Experimental

The solutions of TDAA, TDPA and DTDAA (Evan's), IDAA (Sigma), ODAA (John Backer), nickel sulphate (NiSO₄·H₂O, A.R.) and copper sulphate (CuSO₄·5H₂O, A.R.) were prepared in double distilled water. Perchloric acid (0.04 M)

solution was prepared from the stock solution by dilution with double distilled water and standardised against standard NaOH solution. Other chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The stock solutions of nickel sulphate and copper sulphate were standardised gravimetrically.

A Philips (PR 9405 M) pH meter with glass and calomel electrodes assembly was used to measure the pH. The instrument was calibrated at pH 4.0 and 9.2. The experimental details were the same as reported earlier¹¹. An appropriate quantity of sodium perchlorate (2.0 M) was added to maintain the desired ionic concentrations at 0.1, 0.2 and 0.3 M.

Results and Discussion

The pH range investigated for Ni^{II}-TDAA, Ni^{II}-TDPA, Ni^{II}-DTDAA, Ni^{II}-IDAA, Ni^{II}-ODAA, Cu^{II}-TDAA, Cu^{II}-TDPA, Cu^{II}-IDAA and Cu^{II}-ODAA systems were 2.45-4.80, 3.60-4.70, 3.50-4.70, 2.80-6.80, 3.40-5.20, 2.40-5.20, 3.20-4.40, 2.40-7.40 and 2.60-3.20, respectively.

The proton-ligand stability constants of TDAA, TDPA, DTDAA, IDAA and ODAA, and the stepwise formation constants of their chelates with Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} were determined at 25±0.5, 35±0.5 and 45±0.5° using Irving-Rossotti technique and the values were further refined using the computational techniques^{12,13}, (i) curvefitting method and (ii) pointwise calculation method. The protonation constant values of TDAA, TDPA, DTDAA, IDAA and ODAA determined at different ionic concentrations and temperatures are the same as reported earlier⁶. The stepwise formation constants of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} chelates are given in Table 1.

In Ni^{II}-TDPA, Ni^{II}-DTDAA, Ni^{II}-ODAA, Cu^{II}-TDPA and Cu^{II}-ODAA systems, the $\bar{n}$ values varied between 0.1 and 0.9, thereby indicating the formation of only 1:1 complex. In Ni^{II}-TDAA, Ni^{II}-IDAA, Cu^{II}-TDAA and Cu^{II}-IDAA systems, $\bar{n}$ values varied between 0.2 and 1.9, indicating the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. Cu^{II}-DTDAA systems could not be studied as precipitation starts from the very beginning.

It is evident from Table 1 that metal-ligand formation constants increase with increase in ionic strength and decrease with increase in temperature. The thermodynamic formation constants were evaluated by extrapolating the concentration formation constants to zero ionic strength and the values are given in Table 1. The general trend in the overall thermodynamic stabilities indicates that the Cu^{II} complexes are more stable as compared to the Ni^{II} complexes.

The thermodynamic functions ΔG , ΔH and ΔS were calculated using the standard equations¹⁴ and the values are given in Table 2. Chelates of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with the ligands are formed spontaneously as revealed by the negative ΔG values. The overall changes in ΔH and ΔS values indicate that

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Ni^{II} AND Cu^{II} COMPLEXES

System	Formation constants	Temp. 25°			Ionic strength		
		0.1	0.2	0.3	0.1 35°	0.1 45°	0.0 25°
Ni ^{II} -TDAA	log K ₁	4.26	4.49	4.66	4.26	4.23	4.07
	log K ₂	2.83	2.99	3.20	2.78	2.75	2.64
Ni ^{II} -TDPA	log K ₁	3.86	3.47	3.56	3.93	3.31	3.23
Ni ^{II} -DTDAA	log K ₁	2.84	2.89	2.91	2.83	2.78	2.81
Ni ^{II} -IDAA	log K ₁	3.22	3.27	3.81	3.21	3.18	3.17
	log K ₂	6.03	6.05	6.10	5.96	5.92	6.00
Ni ^{II} -ODAA	log K ₁	2.74	2.77	2.81	2.72	2.69	2.70
Cu ^{II} -TDAA	log K ₁	4.63	4.66	4.69	4.61	4.60	4.60
	log K ₂	2.81	2.83	2.84	2.81	2.77	2.79
Cu ^{II} -TDPA	log K ₁	3.96	4.01	4.05	3.93	3.92	3.92
Cu ^{II} -IDAA	log K ₁	3.63	3.68	3.72	3.59	3.55	3.58
	log K ₂	5.80	5.88	5.94	5.78	5.76	5.73
Cu ^{II} -ODAA	log K ₁	3.95	3.99	4.03	3.93	3.89	3.91

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF Ni^{II} AND Cu^{II} COMPLEXES

System	$\mu=0.1 M$		
	$-\Delta G$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H$ kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS cal deg ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Ni ^{II} -TDAA	9.67	2.85	22.13
Ni ^{II} -TDPA	4.58	1.34	10.51
Ni ^{II} -DTDAA	3.87	1.66	7.17
Ni ^{II} -IDAA	19.44	3.25	52.52
Ni ^{II} -ODAA	3.74	1.72	6.55
Cu ^{II} -TDAA	10.16	3.32	22.16
Cu ^{II} -TDPA	5.40	1.04	14.15
Cu ^{II} -IDAA	19.68	3.73	50.46
Cu ^{II} -ODAA	5.39	1.90	11.82

the complexes are both enthalpy and entropy stabilized. The relatively smaller values of ΔH in comparison to that of ΔS indicate that entropy is the principal driving force for the complex formation in aqueous solution.

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Studies on L-2-Aminomercaptopropionic Acid Metal Complex Equilibria

SALEEM IFTEKHAR and K. P. DUBEY

Department of Chemistry, University of Kashmir, Srinagar-190 006

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OUT of sulphur containing amino acids, the investigation on the complexes of D-penicillamine and L-2-aminomercaptopropionic acid are reported in literature¹. In this note we report our results on stepwise stability constants of L-2-aminomercaptopropionic acid with Be^{II}, La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Au^{III}, Zr^{IV}, Pt^{IV}, Th^{IV} and U^{VI}O₂. We have evaluated thermodynamic parameters from the values obtained on stability constants using temperature coefficient and Gibbs-Helmholtz equation².